

REVIEW

Effect of micronutrients on fertility and aneuploidy rates in human conceptions: a systematic review and meta-analysis

BIOGRAPHY

David Schütz completed his pharmacy studies at Heidelberg University (Germany). In 2024, he started his PhD research at the University of Copenhagen (Denmark) and Ghent University (Belgium) where he is focusing on cytogenetic effects of ageing in human oocytes.

KEY MESSAGE

Sixty-six micronutrients were investigated, and evidence was found to show that coenzyme Q10 (CoQ10) supplementation for women undergoing fertility treatment improves several (pre)clinical outcomes. In in-vitro maturation protocols, CoQ10 increases the oocyte maturation rate and reduces the aneuploidy rate. This suggests that CoQ10 can improve the efficacy of fertility treatment.

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ABSTRACT

In order to make clinical recommendations based on uncertain evidence, a systematic review and meta-analysis on the influence of micronutrient supplementation on preclinical and clinical reproductive outcomes was undertaken. PubMed and Scopus were searched until 12 November 2024. Parallel-grouped intervention studies with women undergoing fertility treatment with micronutrient supplementation or addition of micronutrient to in-vitro maturation media were included. The primary outcomes were oocyte maturation and chromosome aneuploidy rates, pregnancy rate, miscarriage rate, and live birth rate. Five of 1810 studies were included. In three clinical studies, 326 women underwent fertility treatment with coenzyme Q10 (CoQ10) or control treatment. CoQ10 increased oocyte retrieval and live birth rates for women diagnosed with poor ovarian response (POR; OR = 2.28), and increased the pregnancy rate for women diagnosed with POR or polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) (OR = 2.20 and 13.26, respectively). CoQ10 had no effect on the miscarriage rate. In two in-vitro studies, 127 women donated 241 immature oocytes which were matured with CoQ10 or resveratrol. CoQ10 increased the oocyte maturation rate (OR = 2.73), and decreased oocyte and chromosome aneuploidy rates (OR = 0.31 and 0.57, respectively) for women of advanced maternal age (AMA). Resveratrol had no effect. Women of AMA and women diagnosed with POR or PCOS gained greater benefit from CoQ10 supplementation.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decades, couples in high-income economies continue to postpone parenthood

(Schmidt *et al.*, 2012). The lifetime prevalence of infertility is approximately 17.5% in the world population (World Health Organization, 2023). Advanced maternal age (AMA) is associated with a significantly reduced clinical pregnancy

rate (CPR) (Belloc *et al.*, 2008), with contributing factors being ovarian ageing including follicular depletion (Richardson *et al.*, 1987), oocyte maturation deficiency (Wu *et al.*, 2000), oocyte aneuploidy (missing or additional chromosomes)

KEY WORDS

Aneuploidy
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Coenzyme Q10
CoQ10
Resveratrol

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(*Gruhn et al., 2019*) and associated embryo implantation failure (*van Kooij et al., 1996*), and embryo (*Hardy et al., 2001*) and fetal (*Spandorfer et al., 2004*) loss. The oocyte aneuploidy rate is critically influenced by maternal age, following a U-curve: women aged between 20 and 32 years show the lowest level of aneuploid eggs (approximately 20%), while the age groups < 20 years and >32 years exhibit higher levels of aneuploidy which severely limit pregnancy success and fertility (*Gruhn et al., 2019*). The age dependency of oocyte aneuploidy has been reviewed recently (*Gruhn and Hoffmann, 2022*). AMA, generally defined as ≥ 35 years (reviewed by *Mills and Lavender, 2011*), is therefore associated with a lower success rate for assisted reproductive technology (ART) (*O'Brien et al., 2017; Wang et al., 2008*).

Many patients take various supplements to improve pregnancy outcomes and the ART success rate (*Schaefer and Nock, 2019*). However, numerous studies have shown no effect of supplements on reproductive outcomes (*Abadia et al., 2016; Franasiak et al., 2015; Morsy et al., 2020*). Nutritional groups can generally be divided into two major classes: macronutrients and micronutrients. Macronutrients (i.e. carbohydrates, proteins and fats) are consumed in large amounts to make up most of an individual's daily caloric intake. Micronutrients do not play a major role in energy intake, but are nevertheless central for metabolic processes (*Savarino et al., 2021*). A comprehensive list of micronutrients is lacking in the scientific literature. The World Health Organization (WHO) considers vitamins and various metals as micronutrients (*World Health Organization, 2024*). By supplementing micronutrients before and during fertility treatment, possible deficiencies could be corrected to improve physiological functions of importance for reproduction (*Sekhon et al., 2010*). Further, some micronutrients can intercept reactive oxygen species (*Bendich et al., 1986*), thereby reducing the damage to cellular components. In-vitro studies of bovine oocytes showed that oxygenic stress led to decreased maturation (*Iwata et al., 2011*) and increased abnormal fertilization rates (*Takeo et al., 2013*).

Micronutrient supplements are not registered as medicinal products but as dietary supplements, and do not need to comply with Good Manufacturing Practice in the European Union (*Zovi et al., 2025*) or undergo clinical trials (*Charen and*

Harbord, 2020; Petroczi et al., 2011). This can result in substantial health risks (*Charen and Harbord, 2020; van der Voet et al., 2008*), as the bioavailability of newly marketed dietary supplements is usually unknown, and use of the respective products during fertility treatment lacks evidence. However, previous systematic reviews found that many women exhibit insufficient concentrations of various micronutrients during preconception and childbearing life, both in high-income (*Blumfield et al., 2013*) and low-to-middle-income economies (*Darnton-Hill and Mkpuru, 2015*), and that the supplementation of multiple micronutrients could reduce pregnancy complications, such as low birth weight (*Zerfu and Ayele, 2013*).

This systematic review and meta-analysis was conducted to support evidence-based decisions about the clinical use of single micronutrients during fertility treatment.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This systematic review followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines (*Liberati et al., 2009*), and was registered on PROSPERO (CRD42024598515, 14 November 2024) (*PROSPERO, 2024*). The protocol was updated in February 2025 to include the outcome 'chromosome aneuploidy frequency', update the risk-of-bias assessment tool (RoB 2), and include randomized non-placebo-controlled studies. The protocol was updated again in May 2025 for a clearer distinction between the primary and secondary outcomes.

Study selection

Based on the objective of this review, eligibility criteria were developed using the Patient, Intervention, Comparator, Outcome, Study Design (PICOS) scheme (*Brown et al., 2006*).

Participants in the included studies were women of all ages with a 46;XX karyotype undergoing fertility treatment for any indication. Intervention studies with a random assignment of participants or human oocytes to parallel study arms were included. For randomized clinical trials, the included intervention was single micronutrient supplementation. The comparators were placebo treatment or no treatment. For in-vitro studies, the included intervention was addition of a

single micronutrient to in-vitro maturation (IVM) medium used for IVM of germinal vesicle oocytes. The comparator was IVM media with addition of the respective solvent alone.

The primary outcomes of interest were number/proportion of retrieved metaphase II oocytes; oocyte maturation rate; aneuploidy rate/frequency of metaphase II oocytes/zygotes and/or polar bodies; aneuploidy rate/frequency in preimplantation embryos; aneuploidy rate/frequency in ongoing pregnancies; aneuploidy rate/frequency in fetal losses; aneuploidy rate/frequency in live births; and the maternal origin of these aneuploidies. The secondary outcomes were pregnancy rate, miscarriage rate and live birth rate (LBR) after single embryo transfer.

In total, 66 micronutrients were included in this systematic review. The selection of micronutrients was based, in part, on the Micronutrients Database developed by WHO (*World Health Organization, 2024*), which includes 17 micronutrients: calcium; copper; fluoride; folate; iodine; iron; magnesium; riboflavin; selenium; thiamine; vitamin A/B6/B12/C/D/E; and zinc.

Furthermore, a search for small molecules used in ageing-related supplementation was conducted via ClinicalTrials.gov by selecting the condition 'ageing' and the intervention 'supplement'. The exact compounds in the supplements had to be declared and have a molecular mass of ≤ 1000 Da to be included. These supplements were: TA-65, AC-11, curcumin, resveratrol, sesamin, acetyl-L-carnitine, lipoic acid, quercetin, NAD3, hydroxymethylbutyrate, NT-20, 5'-AMP, 5'-CMP, 5'-GMP, 5'-UMP, phosphoglyceric acid, docosahexaenoic acid, eicosapentaenoic acid, secoisolariciresinol diglucoside, lutein, zeaxanthin, taurine, anthocyanin, astaxanthin, lycopene, phosphatidylserine, nicotinamide riboside, fisetin, sodium phosphate, AT-001, α -ketoglutarate, maltodextrin, acetylcholine, sodium nitroprusside, 2-hydroxybenzylamine, astragaloside A, coenzyme Q10 (CoQ10), rutin, nicotinamide mononucleotide, pterostilbene, apigenin and oleuropein (*ClinicalTrials.gov, 2024*).

Finally, the electron transferring coenzymes nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide, nicotinamide adenine dinucleotide phosphate, glutathione,

haem, lipoamide and pyrroloquinoline quinone were included, as they are crucial for cellular protection against oxidative stress (Fedurco, 2000; Kröger and Klingenberg, 1971; Kumar and Kozłowski, 2009; Prütz et al., 1994; Takeda and Nakamura, 2021; Tsai et al., 1983).

Search strategy

The systematic literature search was conducted using PubMed and Scopus, and was limited to studies published in English until 12 November 2024. A manual literature research was performed until 8 January 2025. Exact strings for the systematic search are given in the supplementary data (Supplementary Table 1) for both databases. The systematic search was conducted again prior to submission (21 May 2025). No further articles were included.

Data collection and analysis

The identified records were uploaded to Covidence, a software platform supporting review processes (Covidence, 2024). Screening of the title, abstract and full-text was conducted independently by two investigators (KHL and DS, or ERH and DS) following prespecified inclusion and exclusion criteria (Supplementary Table 2). Conflicts were discussed between the two investigators involved until consensus was achieved.

Two investigators (KHL and DS) independently extracted the data from each eligible study using a data extraction template (Supplementary Table 2). The included outcomes were number of retrieved oocytes, oocyte maturation rate, oocyte aneuploidy rate, oocyte chromosome aneuploidy frequency, CPR, miscarriage rate and LBR.

All studies with the same outcome were included in a meta-analysis. All analyses were conducted in R (version 4.5.1) (R Core Team, 2025). A random-effects model with restricted maximum likelihood estimator was used to calculate OR and corresponding 95% CI for the meta-analysis of dichotomous outcomes that were depicted as forest plots. *P*-values were calculated using two-sided Fisher's exact test without mid-*P* adjustment for cell counts less than five. For higher cell counts, *P*-values were calculated using a two-sided chi-squared test. Statistical significance was assumed for *P* < 0.05. Interstudy heterogeneity was tested for each meta-analysis using the tau-squared test (Kendall, 1938), Cochran's *Q* test

(Cochran, 1950), H^2 test, and Higgin's and Thompson's I^2 test (Higgins and Thompson, 2002) (a list of R packages used is supplied in Supplementary Table 3). Subgroup analyses were conducted with a random-effects model with restricted maximum likelihood estimator if studies exhibited OR differences >2.

Study quality

The revised Cochrane Risk-of-Bias tool for randomized trials (RoB 2) (Sterne et al., 2019) was applied to assess the risk of bias of the included studies. Two investigators (KHL and DS) independently assessed the included outcomes of each study. Conflicts were discussed between the two investigators until consensus was achieved.

Missing numbers were calculated if percentual rates were available. Missing summary statistics for individual studies were calculated when possible. Reporting bias was analysed using the Begg–Mazumdar test (Begg and Mazumdar, 1994) (with *P* > 0.1 indicating no publication bias) and depicted as funnel plots. Confidence in evidence was evaluated following the Grading of Recommendations Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) approach with a grading system out of 4, with 4/4 indicating the highest level of confidence (GRADE Working Group, 2025; Schünemann et al., 2003).

RESULTS

Search results

The combined search yielded 1810 initial results; of these, 504 studies underwent title and abstract screening. As a result, 492 studies were excluded, one randomized controlled trial with CoQ10 administration was retrieved as an abstract alone (Taylor et al., 2018), and 11 studies proceeded to full-text review. Of these, six studies were excluded (Du et al., 2024; El Refaiey et al., 2014; Gat et al., 2016; Gurgan et al., 2011; Pasquariello et al., 2019; Su et al., 2023) (reasons for exclusion are supplied in Supplementary Table 4), and five studies were included in this systematic review (Bentov et al., 2014; Izhar et al., 2022; Liu et al., 2018; Ma et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2018). FIGURE 1 depicts the flow diagram of the study selection process.

Description of studies

Of the five studies included in this systematic review, three were clinical trials

and two were in-vitro studies with human oocytes. Studies were conducted between 2010 and 2020. Micronutrients included in the five studies were CoQ10 (four studies) (Bentov et al., 2014; Izhar et al., 2022; Ma et al., 2020; Xu et al., 2018) and resveratrol (one study) (Liu et al., 2018). An overview of the included studies is provided in TABLE 1.

Participants

In total, 326 women undergoing fertility treatment participated in the clinical trials, including 24 women of AMA (Bentov et al., 2010), 133 women with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) (Izhar et al., 2022), and 169 women with poor ovarian response (POR) (Xu et al., 2018). Furthermore, 127 women donated 241 germinal vesicle oocytes which underwent IVM, including 74 oocytes from 18 women not of AMA. TABLE 1 shows the participants' characteristics. The largest study by Xu et al. (2018) included 169 women: 76 in the treatment arm and 93 in the control arm.

Interventions and comparators

Only CoQ10 and resveratrol were used as interventions in the five included studies. In clinical trials, treatment with CoQ10 ranged from 120 mg to 600 mg per day (Bentov et al., 2014; Izhar et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2018), with treatment length ranging from 60 to 90 days (Bentov et al., 2014; Xu et al., 2018). Comparators were placebo treatment or no treatment. The study by Bentov et al. (2014) was terminated prematurely.

In the in-vitro studies, the intervention groups of germinal vesicle oocytes were matured in IVM media with 50 μ M CoQ10 (ethanol solution) for 24–48 h (Ma et al., 2020), or 1.0 μ M resveratrol (in DMSO solution) for 24 or 36 h (Liu et al., 2018). Comparators were standard IVM media with equivalent volumes of ethanol or DMSO, respectively.

Outcomes

All clinical trials reported CPR, and both in-vitro studies reported the oocyte maturation rate. Further outcomes were given in some studies (TABLE 1).

Study design

One study was a randomized placebo-controlled double-blinded clinical trial (Bentov et al., 2014). Two studies were randomized, non-treatment-controlled and double-blinded until allocation; after allocation, both participants and staff were made aware of the interventions (Izhar et al., 2022; Xu et al., 2018). For the two in-

FIGURE 1 PRISMA flow chart for study inclusion. Initially, 1810 records were identified. Of these, 1306 were recognized automatically as duplicates, and 504 were retrieved for title and abstract screening. Of the screened records, 492 were excluded and 12 were sought to be retrieved for full-text screening, but this was only completed for 11 records. Of these, six studies were excluded, and five studies were included in the review.

in vitro studies, randomizations were performed, and the studies were partially blinded (Liu *et al.*, 2018; Ma *et al.*, 2020). The laboratory staff were aware of the allocation, but the staff performing the bioinformatic analysis were blinded.

Risk-of-bias analysis

The results of the risk-of-bias analysis are presented in [FIGURE 2](#). The studies by Ma *et al.* (2020) and Xu *et al.* (2018) were assessed with ‘some concerns’ in ‘selection of the reported data’ solely because they reported no prespecified analysis plan. As it was considered unlikely that the reported numerical data were selected, this still led to an overall assessment of low risk. The studies by Bentov *et al.* (2014) and

Liu *et al.* (2018) exhibit some risk as they were underpowered. Despite the initial diagnosis as anovulatory and resistant to clomiphene citrate, four of 63 women in the control group in the study by Izhari *et al.* (2022) conceived naturally while receiving clomiphene citrate alone. As the inclusion and allocation of these four women seems unsuitable, this study exhibits a high risk of bias.

With one exception in CPR, the results did not show evidence of reporting bias, but had low validity as only two to three groups were included for the respective analyses ([Supplementary Table 5](#), [Supplementary Figures A.1–A.6](#)). Interstudy heterogeneity was low for most results, but oocyte

aneuploidy rate *in vitro* and CPR had moderate and high heterogeneity, respectively ([Supplementary Table 6](#)).

Effects of interventions

Effect of micronutrients on preclinical outcomes

Resveratrol. One in-vitro study addressed the effect of 1.0 μM resveratrol in IVM media on the maturation rate of germinal vesicle oocytes from women of AMA (38–45 years) (Liu *et al.*, 2018). Repeated measurements were taken after 24 and 36 h (endpoint). For both timepoints, increased maturation rates (OR ≥ 2.00) with equivocal *P*-values were

TABLE 1 OVERVIEW OF INCLUDED STUDIES

Study ID	Study design	Trial registration number	Country	Micronutrient	Participants	Intervention	Control	Measured outcomes	Results
Bentov et al., 2014	Randomized placebo-controlled trial, double-blinded	NCT01048385	Canada	CoQ10	Women of AMA undergoing IVF/ICSI, 35–43 years of age, <i>n</i> = 24	600 mg CoQ10 (6 × 100 mg once a day) for 2 months or up to three cycles, <i>n</i> = 10	Placebo (6 × once a day) for 2 months or up to three cycles, <i>n</i> = 14	OAR, CPR, LBR	OAR: 46.44% ± 13.9 versus 62.77% ± 9.3, not significant (reported), <i>P</i> = 0.10 (calculated) CPR: 33.3% versus 26.7%, not significant (reported), <i>P</i> = 0.71 (calculated) LBR: 25.0% versus 26.7%, not significant (reported), <i>P</i> = 1.0 (calculated)
Izhar et al., 2022	Randomized controlled trial, double-blind allocation, but only blinded for investigators after allocation	NCT04302532	Pakistan	CoQ10	Women diagnosed with CC-resistant PCOS in need of induced ovulation, mean age: 28–29 years, <i>n</i> = 133	120 mg CoQ10 (once a day) + 150 mg CC oral tablets (3 × 50 mg, three times a day), <i>n</i> = 70	150 mg CC oral tablets (3 × 50 mg, three times a day), <i>n</i> = 63	CPR	CPR: 34/70 (48.6%) versus 4/63 (6.3%), <i>P</i> = 0.001
Liu et al., 2018	Randomized controlled trial, investigators were not blinded, patients were blinded		China	Resveratrol	Women of AMA undergoing ICSI, 38–45 years of age, <i>n</i> = 64 (<i>n</i> = 75 GV oocytes)	1.0 μmol/l resveratrol in IVM media solution for 24 or 36 h, <i>n</i> = 38	Equivalent volume of DMSO in IVM media solution for 24 or 36 h, <i>n</i> = 37	OMR	OMR after 24 h: 21/38 (55.3%) versus 14/37 (37.8%), <i>P</i> < 0.05 (reported); <i>P</i> = 0.130 (calculated), not significant OMR after 36 h: 27/38 (71.1%) versus 19/37 (51.4%), <i>P</i> < 0.05 (reported); <i>P</i> = 0.08 (calculated), not significant
Ma et al., 2020	Randomized controlled trial, investigators were not blinded, patients were blinded (not a human clinical study)		China	CoQ10	Women of AMA and not of AMA undergoing IVF, Group 1: ≥38 years, <i>n</i> = 45 women (<i>n</i> = 92 GV oocytes). Group 2: ≤30 years, <i>n</i> = 18 women (<i>n</i> = 74 GV oocytes)	50 μmol/l CoQ10 in IVM media solution for 24–48 h, Group 1: <i>n</i> = 46 oocytes, Group 2: <i>n</i> = 35 oocytes	0.5% ethanol in IVM media solution for 24–48 h. Group 1: <i>n</i> = 46 oocytes, Group 2: <i>n</i> = 39 oocytes	OMR, OAR, CAR	Women of AMA: OMR: 38/46 (82.6%) versus 29/46 (63.0%), <i>P</i> = 0.035 OAR: 14/38 (36.8%) versus 19/29 (65.5%), <i>P</i> = 0.020 CAR: 36/874 (4.1%) versus 47/667 (7.0%), <i>P</i> = 0.012 Women not of AMA:

(continued on next page)

TABLE 1 (Continued)

Study ID	Study design	Trial registration number	Country	Micronutrient	Participants	Intervention	Control	Measured outcomes	Results
									OMR: 28/35 (80.0%) versus 30/39 (76.9%), $P = 0.748$, not significant OAR: 8/28 (28.6%) versus 9/30 (30.0%), $P = 0.905$, not significant CAR: 15/644 (2.3%) versus 24/690 (3.5%), $P = 0.213$, not significant
Xu et al., 2018	Randomized controlled trial, double-blinded allocation, but unblinded after allocation	ChiCTR-IPR-17010945	China	CoQ10	Women diagnosed with POR undergoing IVF, mean age: 32–32.5 years, $n = 169$	600 mg oral CoQ10 (1 × 200 mg, three times a day) for 60 days, $n = 76$	No treatment, $n = 93$	MR, LBR	CPR: 24/76 (31.58%) versus 16/93 (17.20%), $P = 0.11$, not significant, $P = 0.03$ (calculated) MR: 2/24 (8.33%) versus 2/16 (12.50%), $P = 0.73$ (reported), $P = 1.0$ (calculated), not significant LBR: 22/76 (28.95%) versus 14/93 (15.54%), $P = 0.08$, not significant

AMA, advanced maternal age; IVM, in-vitro maturation; ICSI, intracytoplasmic sperm injection; CoQ10, coenzyme Q10; CC, clomiphene citrate; DMSO, dimethylsulfoxide; CAR, chromosome aneuploidy rate; OMR, oocyte maturation rate; OAR, oocyte aneuploidy rate; CPR, clinical pregnancy rate; LBR, live birth rate; MR, miscarriage rate; GV, germinal vesicle; PCOS, polycystic ovary syndrome; POR, poor ovarian response.

FIGURE 2 Risk-of-bias results for the included studies using the RoB 2 tool. The overall assessments suggest low ('low risk'), medium ('some concerns') or high risk ('high risk') of over- or underestimation of the effect of the respective intervention.

detected [after 36 h: 71.05% versus 51.35%, $P = 0.080$ (reported: $P < 0.05$); after 24 h: 55.26% versus 37.84%, $P = 0.130$ (reported: $P < 0.05$); **FIGURE 3**]. For the endpoint measurement, a power of 0.765 was calculated. Confidence in evidence was assessed as low (2/4), as the endpoint measurement showed a clear direction of effect but was underpowered.

Coenzyme Q10. The study by *Xu et al.* (2018) was the only study to report the number of retrieved oocytes in full [as median (with quartile 1 and quartile 3)] after CoQ10 supplementation. A significant difference between the treatment group [4 (2, 5)] and the control group [2 (1, 4)] was discovered ($P = 0.002$). Confidence in evidence for the number of retrieved oocytes was assessed as moderate (3/4), as only one clinical trial reported a large effect size.

One in-vitro study investigated the effect of 50 μM CoQ10 supplementation on the maturation rates of germinal vesicle oocytes from women of AMA (>37 years) and women not of AMA (<31 years) which underwent IVM for 24–48 h (*Ma et al.*, 2020). For both age groups combined, CoQ10 demonstrated no effect (81.48%

versus 69.41%, OR = 1.92, 95% CI 0.94–4.07; $P = 0.076$; **FIGURE 3**). However, oocytes from women of AMA showed a significant increase in the maturation rate (82.61% versus 63.04%; $P = 0.035$), whereas oocytes from women not of AMA showed no effect of CoQ10 on the maturation rate (80.00% versus 76.92%; $P = 0.748$). Confidence in evidence was assessed as moderate (3/4), as a highly age-dependent effect of large effect size was detected by one study alone.

The one in-vitro study that investigated the oocyte aneuploidy rate (*Ma et al.*, 2020) assessed the oocytes that reached maturation after IVM with or without CoQ10 supplementation. For the two defined age groups combined, CoQ10 treatment compared to control treatment caused, no significant change in the oocyte aneuploidy rate (33.33% versus 47.46%, OR = 0.56, 95% CI 0.27–1.15; $P = 0.14$). For women of AMA, a significant reduction in the aneuploidy rate was measured for CoQ10-treated oocytes compared to control-treated oocytes (36.84% versus 65.52%; $P = 0.020$), whereas no change was seen in CoQ10-treated oocytes compared to control-treated oocytes retrieved from women not of AMA

(28.57% versus 30.00%; $P = 0.905$; **FIGURE 3**). Once more, confidence in evidence was assessed as moderate (3/4), as only one study detected a large age-related effect.

Additionally, the oocyte aneuploidy rate was assessed in one clinical trial with oral CoQ10 supplementation in women of AMA (*Bentov et al.*, 2014). The oocytes from women of AMA showed a reduction in the aneuploidy rate, which did not reach significance (46.34% versus 62.16%, OR = 0.53, 95% CI 0.24–1.15; $P = 0.12$; **FIGURE 3**). However, as this randomized controlled trial was terminated prematurely and was therefore underpowered, confidence in evidence was assessed as low (2/4).

One in-vitro study investigated the effect of CoQ10 on chromosome aneuploidy frequency in metaphase II oocytes after IVM (*Ma et al.*, 2020). Overall, the treatment decreased chromosome aneuploidy frequency (3.36% versus 5.23%, OR = 0.63, 95% CI 0.43–0.91; $P = 0.016$). For women of AMA, a significant effect was shown (4.12% versus 7.05%; $P = 0.012$). The women not of AMA exhibited generally lower levels of

Oocyte maturation rate after resveratrol treatment

Oocyte maturation rate after coenzyme Q10 treatment

Oocyte aneuploidy rate after in vitro maturation

Oocyte aneuploidy rate after clinical supplementation

Chromosome aneuploidy frequency

FIGURE 3 Effects of micronutrient supplementation on preclinical outcomes. Age specifications indicate that outcomes were investigated in women of the respective age group without collective diagnoses of polycystic ovary syndrome or poor ovarian response. All statistical analyses were conducted using a random-effects model with restricted maximum likelihood estimator. CoQ10, coenzyme Q10.

aneuploid chromosomes, but CoQ10 supplementation showed no significant effect (2.33% versus 3.48%; $P = 0.213$; [FIGURE 3](#)). As an age-dependent effect with a large effect size was reported for the women of AMA but only one study was included, confidence in evidence was assessed as moderate (3/4).

Effect of micronutrients on clinical outcomes

Oral CoQ10 supplementation increased CPR in women undergoing fertility

treatment (39.24% versus 14.04%, OR = 3.93, 95% CI 2.32–6.83; $P < 0.001$) based on three studies included in this meta-analysis. Increased CPR after treatment with CoQ10 was seen in women not of AMA with diagnosed POR [31.58% versus 17.20%; $P = 0.023$ (reported: $P = 0.11$)] ([Xu et al., 2018](#)) and in women not of AMA with clomiphene-citrate-resistant PCOS (48.57% versus 6.35%; $P < 0.001$) ([Izhar et al., 2022](#)), but no effect was seen in women of AMA without a diagnosis of PCOS

(33.33% versus 26.67%; $P = 0.516$) ([Bentov et al., 2014](#)) ([FIGURE 4](#)).

Confidence in evidence was assessed as moderate (3/4), due to the same effect direction but different effect sizes and wide CI.

One clinical trial investigated the effect of CoQ10 on the miscarriage rate in women aged <35 years diagnosed with POR ([Xu et al., 2018](#)); no effect was found (8.33% versus 12.50%, OR = 0.64, 95% CI 0.06–6.78; $P = 1.00$; [FIGURE 4](#)). Confidence

Clinical pregnancy rate

Miscarriage rate

Live birth rate

FIGURE 4 Effects of micronutrient supplementation on clinical outcomes. Age specifications indicate that outcomes were investigated in women of the respective age group without collective diagnoses of polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) or poor ovarian response (POR). 'PCOS' indicates that the outcome was investigated in women not of advanced maternal age (AMA) diagnosed with PCOS. 'POR' indicates that the outcome was investigated in women not of AMA with poor ovarian response. All statistical analyses were conducted using a random-effects model with restricted maximum likelihood estimator. CoQ10, coenzyme Q10.

in evidence was assessed as low (2/4), due to the very low number of participants, limited statistical power, and wide CI for the only included study.

Overall, oral CoQ10 supplementation resulted in an insignificant increase in LBR (28.41% versus 16.67%, OR = 1.97, 95% CI 0.99–3.98; $P = 0.057$). For women not of AMA diagnosed with POR, a significant increase in LBR was detected [28.95% versus 15.05%; $P = 0.023$ (reported: $P = 0.08$)] (Xu et al., 2018), but for women of AMA without a diagnosis of POR, no effect on LBR was reported (25.0% versus 26.7%; $P = 0.702$; FIGURE 4) (Bentov et al., 2014). Confidence in evidence provided by Bentov et al. (2014) was assessed as low (2/4), due to lower statistical power and imprecise CI. Confidence in evidence provided by Xu et al. (2018) was assessed as moderate (3/4), as the effect size was great and the CI was relatively narrow.

Subgroup analysis for clinical pregnancy rate

As women with diagnosed PCOS exhibited a difference in OR >10 for CPR compared

with women diagnosed with POR but not diagnosed with PCOS, and women of AMA not diagnosed with either POR or PCOS, and due to high interstudy heterogeneity ($I^2 = 76.25\%$; Supplementary Table 6), a subgroup analysis was conducted. CoQ10 supplementation still led to an increased CPR for women not diagnosed with PCOS (31.81% versus 18.52%, OR = 2.04, 95% CI 1.06–4.01; $P = 0.044$) (Bentov et al., 2014; Xu et al., 2018), and a greater increase for women diagnosed with PCOS (48.57% versus 6.35%, OR = 13.26, 95% CI 4.77–48.47; $P < 0.001$) (Izhar et al., 2022). No other meta-analysis met the criterion for a subgroup analysis.

DISCUSSION

This systematic review and meta-analysis investigated the evidence for use of the micronutrients CoQ10 and resveratrol in fertility treatment. CoQ10 strongly increased the maturation rate of oocytes retrieved from women of AMA, while the effect size of resveratrol was substantial but was not accompanied by low risk of a type I

error (P -value). Furthermore, CoQ10 reduced the oocyte aneuploidy rate and chromosome aneuploidy frequency, and increased the number of retrieved oocytes and CPR. CoQ10 was not found to have a significant effect on miscarriage rate or LBR.

Regarding the oocyte maturation rate, the greater effect size of CoQ10 (Ma et al., 2020) compared with resveratrol (Liu et al., 2018) in women of AMA may be explained by a difference in antioxidative potency, which was not compensated by the choice of concentration (50 μM and 1.0 μM , respectively). In a mouse model, Liu et al. (2018) demonstrated a higher maturation rate with 1.0 μM resveratrol. This effect size for murine oocytes was not reached in human oocytes. For the oocyte aneuploidy rate and chromosome aneuploidy frequency, only women aged ≥ 38 years (Ma et al., 2020) showed a decrease after CoQ10 supplementation. Women aged ≤ 30 years showed no significant decrease in the aneuploidy rate, likely due to the naturally lower occurrence of aneuploidies in this age

group. Due to raised safety concerns regarding embryo quality after polar body 1 biopsy (Levin *et al.*, 2012), the study by Bentov *et al.* (2014) was terminated prematurely. No effect of CoQ10 on the aneuploidy rate was detected, but post-hoc analysis revealed that the study was underpowered.

Similarly, Bentov *et al.* (2014) reported no effect of CoQ10 on CPR. Izhar *et al.* (2022) reported that the ovulation rate of naturally conceiving women diagnosed with PCOS under CoQ10 administration improved from 19.0% to 70.0% ($P < 0.001$). This could explain the higher pregnancy rate for this group (48.6% versus 6.3%). The oocyte aneuploidy rate was not investigated. The increased CPR for women diagnosed with POR detected by Xu *et al.* (2018) was likely caused by the increased median number of retrieved oocytes per stimulation cycle (four versus two). Xu *et al.* (2018) did not detect an effect of CoQ10 on the miscarriage rate, but reported a significant increase in LBR (28.95% versus 15.05%), whereas Bentov *et al.* (2014) reported no effect on LBR. The study by Taylor *et al.* (2018) (excluded as only retrieved as abstract) reported no significant effect of oral CoQ10 administration on the preimplantation embryo euploidy rate [intervention group: 32.4% (11/34); control group: 58.8% (10/17); $P > 0.05$], but showed an unfavourable effect direction, suggesting that relevantly greater sample sizes are needed to investigate this outcome

In a systematic review with meta-analysis, Florou *et al.* (2020) found that CoQ10 increased CPR but had no effect on the miscarriage rate or LBR, which is in accordance with the present results. A previous publication reviewing the influence of various micro- and macronutrients, as well as dietary regimens, on fertility outcomes found that pretreatment with CoQ10 improved the ovarian response to stimulation protocols, and consequently increased the number of retrieved oocytes and embryo quality; however, inconsistent effects of CoQ10 on CPR and the oocyte aneuploidy rate led to an inconclusive assessment of which group of patients might benefit clinically from CoQ10 treatment (Hart, 2024). Other reviews concluded that multivitamin supplementation showed small but beneficial effects on CPR (Grajcki *et al.*, 2012; Schaefer and Nock, 2019) and time to pregnancy (Schaefer and Nock, 2019). As most

studies investigating the role of micronutrients in female fertility are observational, small or address multisubstance administration, randomized controlled trials with single micronutrients, sufficiently powered to detect effects on the miscarriage rate and LBR, are needed.

This review has important limitations. Firstly, only one study could be included for the outcomes 'number of retrieved oocytes' and 'miscarriage rate', respectively, making meta-analyses redundant. Secondly, no effect of CoQ10 was shown for the outcome 'miscarriage rate', and for one study for the outcome 'LBR' (Bentov *et al.*, 2014). The small sample sizes of downstream reproductive outcomes limit the power of these investigations. For some studies, the reported P -values and those calculated by the present authors differed considerably. Xu *et al.* (2018) reported $P > 0.05$ for CPR and LBR, which were identified as $P < 0.05$ by the present authors, whereas Liu *et al.* (2018) claimed a significant increase in the oocyte maturation rate, which could not be confirmed by the present authors. Furthermore, the present study compared different supplementation formulations, single doses, dosing regimens and treatment durations, impeding assumptions about the CoQ10 concentration in blood plasma, follicular fluid or oocytes. In the subgroup analysis for CPR of women with diagnosed PCOS, CoQ10 increased the ovulation rate in anovulatory patients, which could explain the greatly increased OR.

As only one to three studies per outcome were included in this review, analysis of interstudy heterogeneity, reporting bias and outcome syntheses was not possible for the miscarriage rate (Xu *et al.*, 2018), and delivered low-validity results for the other outcomes. However, strengths of this review include the focus on single-entity supplementation regimens, the inclusion of a large variety of micronutrients associated with cellular ageing, the limitation to parallel-grouped studies, and the use of established tools to ensure a systematic, extensive and bias-limited review process.

CONCLUSION

Of 66 investigated micronutrients, this systematic review found evidence for the use of only two: CoQ10 and resveratrol.

Reliable evidence was found that CoQ10-supplemented IVM media increases the maturation rate of oocytes retrieved from women of AMA. No significant effect of resveratrol on the maturation rate was found. Furthermore, this review found strong evidence that in-vitro CoQ10 supplementation decreases the oocyte aneuploidy rate and chromosome aneuploidy frequency in oocytes from women of AMA. Due to insufficient power, no in-vivo effect of CoQ10 on the aneuploidy rate could be shown. Oral CoQ10 supplementation was found to reduce the miscarriage rate insignificantly. Moderate evidence was found for a CoQ10-mediated increase in the number of retrieved oocytes and LBR, as both were increased in women diagnosed with POR alone. Additionally, CoQ10 increased CPR in women diagnosed with POR or PCOS, but not in women of AMA without these diagnoses. These findings suggest that CoQ10 can be used for in-vitro procedures for research purposes only. Further randomized controlled trials are needed to recommend CoQ10 for fertility treatment for women diagnosed with POR or PCOS; promising clinical outcomes (especially increased LBR) were only evident for these women.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

David Schütz: data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology,

project administration, software, visualization, writing — original draft. Kirstine Huong Lettorp: data curation, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, writing — review and editing. Isa Amalie Olofsson: investigation, methodology, validation, writing — review and editing. Eva R. Hoffmann: conceptualization, funding acquisition, project administration, resources, supervision, writing — review and editing. All authors made substantial contributions to: conception and design of the study, or acquisition of data, or analysis and interpretation of data; drafting the article or revising it critically for important intellectual content; and final approval of the version to be submitted.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found in the online version at doi:10.1016/j.rbmo.2025.105261.

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